

EL LENGUAJE DE LOS MEDIOS COMO REFLEJO DE LOS CAMBIOS EN EL MUNDO

MEDIA LANGUAGE AS A REFLECTION OF CHANGES IN THE WORLD

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ABSTRACT

Mass communication affects both society and culture. Different social orders have different media frameworks, and how they are established by law affects how society works. Diverse forms of communication, including messages in the mass media, provide the form and structure of society. Language is an aspect of our culture that is no exception due to the influence of the media. This article is about how television, radio, the Internet and other media can shape our culture and reflect our cultural behavior. The media can control, influence and put pressure on society, along with the fact that they really control the world at times both in a positive and negative sense. In addition, the media can control people in the spotlight to lead their lives in a certain way or rebel against how they "should" be. These possibilities are only growing as devices such as cell phones and tablet computers allow us to access various forms of media from virtually anywhere.

KEY WORDS

Communication technologies, language of the media, television channels, radio, Internet

RESUMEN

La comunicación de masas afecta tanto a la sociedad como a la cultura. Los diferentes órdenes sociales tienen diferentes marcos de medios, y la forma en que se establecen por ley afecta el funcionamiento de la sociedad. Diversas formas de comunicación, incluidos los mensajes en los medios de comunicación de masas, proporcionan la forma y la estructura de la sociedad. El idioma es un aspecto de nuestra cultura que no es una excepción debido a la influencia de los medios de comunicación. Este artículo trata sobre cómo la televisión, la radio, Internet y otros medios pueden moldear nuestra cultura y reflejar nuestro comportamiento cultural. Los medios de comunicación pueden controlar, influir y presionar a la sociedad, además de que realmente controlan el mundo a veces tanto en un sentido positivo como negativo. Además, los medios de comunicación pueden controlar a las personas en el centro de atención para que lleven sus vidas de cierta manera o se rebelen contra cómo "deberían" ser. Estas posibilidades solo están creciendo a medida que dispositivos como teléfonos celulares y tabletas nos permiten acceder a varias formas de medios desde prácticamente cualquier lugar.

PALABRAS CLAVE

Tecnologías de la comunicación, lenguaje de los medios, canales de televisión, radio, Internet

INTRODUCTION

Formation and development of media linguistics as an independent direction in modern linguistics is due to a number of factors, both related to linguistics and to the information-technological and socio-cultural spheres of public life. Among the most significant prerequisites for the emergence of media linguistics are the following:

- the rapid growth of information and communication technologies (ICT), expressed, in particular, in the creation of a global network of media communication;
- formation and development of a single information space as a new virtual environment for text communication;
- the formation and scientific understanding of the concept of "language of the media", the definition of its functional and stylistic features and internal structure; (Alekseeva, 1994, p.63)

- awareness of the need to apply an integrated approach to the study of media speech, based on combining the efforts of representatives of different humanitarian disciplines;
- consideration of studies of the language of the media in the framework of media studies (media studies)
- a new independent discipline, the subject of which is a comprehensive analysis of the historical development, current state and features of the functioning of the entire complex of mass media.

Let's dwell on each of the above factors in more detail. (Alekseeva, 1994, p. 65-66)

II. THE ROLE OF THE MEDIA IN THE DYNAMICS OF LANGUAGE PROCESSES.

The second half of the XX - beginning of the XXI century is characterized by the rapid growth of mass communication and new information technologies. The dynamic development of traditional media - print, radio, television, the emergence and spread of the World Wide Web - the Internet have led to the creation of a single information space, a special virtual environment formed by the aggregate of many media streams. All these affected the processes of production and distribution of the word, on the features of speech use and the nature of linguistic changes. The main volume of speech use today falls on the sphere of mass communication. Mass media texts, or media texts, are one of the most common forms of modern language existence, and their total length exceeds the total volume of speech in other spheres of human activity (Allan Bell, 1995, p.23). At the same time, the corpus of texts produced and transmitted on a daily basis through media channels continues to grow steadily. This, in particular, can be judged by quantitative indicators: the number of television channels is growing (in the USA it reaches more than hundred, including cable television), their further specialization is taking place - there are mainly news channels (for example, CNN - Cable News Network), entertainment (MTV), sports (Eurosport), educational (Discovery Channel), music, etc. New radio stations appear, new newspapers and magazines appear, designed both for a wide audience and for satisfying the interests of a wide variety of age, professional and social groups. (Lapteva, 2000)

Communication on the World Wide Web makes a huge contribution to the constant growth of the mass of media speech. The proliferation of online versions of printed publications, the emergence of online publications - all this contributes to an increase in the total number of texts functioning in the world information space, which

is considered by researchers as a special sphere of speech use with its own characteristics. The concept of a single information space is a key importance for understanding the dynamics of linguistic changes, since it allows us to represent the multifaceted activities of the world and national mass media in the form of a single, holistic system, the functioning of which has a significant impact on the course of linguocultural processes. In modern science, to designate this new virtual territory without state borders and tangible barriers, a whole set of terms and concepts are used that relate to a semantic series, but emphasize one or another side of mass communication processes, such as: information space, information environment, information field, media environment, media landscape, infosphere. The concept of a single information space allows you to better understand the laws of movement of information flows, as well as to present a holistic information picture of the world in dynamics. The most important component of the world information space is its linguocultural component, the importance of which is difficult to overestimate, since any verbally expressed information is the embodiment of a certain language and culture. Understood as the area of distribution of a particular language and culture in the global media landscape, the concept of a linguocultural space allows us to demonstrate the actual discrepancy between the boundaries of territorial, state and the boundaries of information spheres of influence (Berkowitz, 1984, p.414-416). Thus, the real contours of the Anglo-American linguocultural space go far beyond the territories of the respective states due to the huge coverage of English-language media broadcasting and the spread of the Internet.

The role of the media in the dynamics of linguistic processes, it must be emphasized that we mean not only and not so much changes caused by the introduction of new information technologies, but qualitative transformations in the general linguocultural situation. In turn, assessing the impact of modern mass media on the course of linguistic processes, it is possible to distinguish between the following three levels of analysis (Lapteva, 2003):

- geolinguistic
- interlinguistic
- intralinguistic.

The geolinguistic level, as the name implies, involves an analysis of how the media influence the state and development of the general linguocultural situation in the world and in the regions. Here, attention is focused on such important quantitative and areal indicators as a change in the number of speakers in a particular language, a redistribution of linguistic spheres of influence, an increase in the role of some and a decrease in the role of other languages in the world information space.

At the interlinguistic or interlanguage level, researchers are interested in the issues of interaction and mutual influence of languages, the mechanisms and methods of borrowing, as well as functional styles and spheres of speech, are most susceptible to foreign language influence.

Intralinguistic level, or intralingual, allows you to focus on media-conditioned linguistic processes within one linguistic-cultural area. These include: the tendency to blur clear style boundaries, the spread of colloquial style norms in the basic corpus of media speech (news, information analytics, commentary), the replication of erroneous speech use (for example, incorrect stress, grammatical errors and incorrect collocation), a decrease in the speech norm due to the use of in the media with reduced and profanity, etc. Let's dwell on each of the listed levels in more detail. One of the main features of the modern geolinguistic picture of the world is the indisputable dominance of the English language, which manifests itself, among other things, in the field of mass communication. The total volume of English-language media texts, due to a number of economic, political and socio-cultural reasons, significantly exceeds the volume of mass media texts in other languages of the world. Thus, the instant reaction to events anywhere in the world, their objective coverage helped the American world news channel (CNN) gain popularity among viewers around the world. This channel broadcasts in English. BBC World enjoys a reputation as one of the most objective news channels, which is why it is watched in Western Europe, the United States and other countries around the world. Since the beginning of the 90s. in connection with significant socio-economic changes, English-language media are becoming more widespread in many developed countries and developing countries. (Higgins, J.A., Brand Miller, J.C. and Denyer, 1996, p.96)

A. *The lingua franca*

In the mid-90s. where English already began to spread foreign journalists working in Moscow created the Independent Media company, which publishes the popular publications The Moscow Times, The Moscow Tribune, The St. Petersburg Times, Capital, and also oversees the release of Russian-language analogues of well-known magazines: "Cosmopolitan", "Good Housekeeping" and at the beginning of 2000s English language began to spread in Uzbekistan after which was published magazines in English as Magazine "Visit Uzbekistan" - (is the magazine, which truly demonstrates in each issue all the reasons to visit Uzbekistan and even more. To find a reason to visit our unique country more often and perhaps to stay for long. Find your travel or business opportunities or a chance for culture exchange in ethnic festivals or maybe spend a gastronomic journey through the Visit Uzbekistan's pages.) or the

magazine "International relations: politics, economics, law" is an interdisciplinary scientific and theoretical publication of the University of World Economy and Diplomacy of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

All these testify to the further integration and globalization of international information systems and is reflected in the course of language processes, the qualitative aspect of speech use, the movement of language norms, as well as the interaction of languages and cultures. The globalization of the world information space has contributed not only to a significant expansion of the sphere of influence of the English language, but also to its transformation into a generally recognized language of international communication - the lingua franca. Currently, English has become the language of international business and trade, politics and diplomacy, science and information technology, media, popular music, show business, sports and education (Gendina, 2006, p.512). Today it is hardly possible to find a field of human activity in which the English language would not have a dominant meaning. The global role of the English language in the modern world is perfectly described by the famous English linguist David Crystal in his book "English as a Global Language", noting the role of the media in promoting and spreading the English language and mass culture in national media landscapes. Indeed, the total number of media texts in English, distributed daily through media channels, significantly exceeds the number of texts in other languages, and in the national mass media of almost all countries of the world, there is an expansion of samples of English-language mass culture. The Beatles, Madonna, Backstreet Boys, Spice Girls, etc. - a constantly updated list of popular songs in English is well known to a mass audience both in the West and East. In this regard, the concept of linguistic imperialism, which arose within the framework of the Western European academic tradition in the early 90s of the XX century as a reaction to a completely positive assessment of the global role of English in the modern world, is of certain interest. Formulated by the English researcher Robert Phillipson in his book "Linguistic Imperialism" (Rose, Conama, 2018, p.385) the concept of linguistic imperialism considers the dominant role of the English language in the modern world as an expansion in relation to other languages and cultures. It is noted that the rapid increase in the share of the English language in the world linguocultural space is influenced by a number of political and economic factors: from the colonial rule of the British Empire and the transformation of the United States into a world superpower to the information technology revolution and the rapid development of transport networks. Explaining the "world domination" of the English language mainly for socio-economic and political reasons, as well as the promotion of the national interests of the most powerful English-speaking countries - the United States and Great Britain, Robert Phillipson emphasizes that the expansion of the English language causes irreparable damage to other national languages and cultures. The concept of linguistic imperialism is formulated by analogy with the concept of cultural imperialism, already well-

established in Western humanities, with the help of which the content of the socio-economic concept of "imperialism" is extended to the sphere of culture. The term "cultural imperialism» (Weckert, Al-Saggaf, 2003, p. 21) is used to denote the dominant influence of a particular culture, primarily the English-speaking, American culture in the modern world. The modes of cultural influence are many and varied: these are the media, film and video production, advertising, youth culture and popular music, as well as targeted influence in the field of education. Along with linguistic imperialism, researchers also distinguish media or information imperialism. The term media imperialism is used in modern foreign research on the media to denote the redistribution of the world information space in favor of the most powerful and influential countries politically, economically and technologically. For example, renowned American media expert Oliver Boyd-Barrett (2018) defines media imperialism as a state in which the property rights, structure, distribution and content of mass communication are significantly influenced by foreign media organizations. At the same time, in the author's opinion, the unevenness in the implementation of media interaction, the absence of an equivalent exchange of information flows, is of particular importance.

Professor Boyd-Barrett (2018) notes that in such conditions the most powerful leading countries have a dominant influence on the world media space. Thus, the description of linguocultural and informational processes using the socio-economic term imperialism, which has certain negative connotations, allows us to emphasize their aggressive, offensive nature. Indeed, the expansion of the sphere of influence of the English language in the world information space noticeably enhances its impact on other languages, which, in particular, is manifested in a large number of English-language borrowings. In turn, the expansion of the English-speaking mass culture is inevitably accompanied by a reduction in the share of the national media product in the domestic market. And if some countries, for example, France, try to somehow control the English-speaking influence by introducing legislative restrictions, then the cultural and information space of some countries continues to remain completely open. In order to prevent dominant of other culture French schools have special subject "French people behave". Naturally, this affects both the general language situation and the state of the internal media landscape. The study of the role of the media in the dynamics of linguistic processes at the interlinguistic level involves the analysis of media-conditioned mechanisms of interaction of languages, in particular, such as methods of borrowing lexical units, functional-style stratification of borrowings, and the mutual influence of communicative and broadcasting styles. Since in the information society, cultural and linguistic influence is most actively carried out through the channels of mass communication, the dominant influence of the English-language media speech on the world information space, including its national segment, is clearly seen in the analysis of the corresponding media discourses.

III. THE IMPACT OF THE ANGLO-AMERICAN MASS MEDIA ON THE RUSSIAN AND UZBEK MEDIA

A. *Tv programs*

The influence of the Anglo-American mass media on the Russian and Uzbek media is noticeable both at the level of format and content, and at the level of language.

The widespread distribution of English-language samples of television and radio products, copying (both licensed and unlicensed, pirated) of format and content, a powerful wave of English-language borrowing, imitation of communicative and broadcasting styles - all these are characteristic features of modern media texts. One of the most striking examples of the influence of English-language media on the format and content of mass media texts in Russia are programs modeled on well-known Western programs. Thus, many popular projects of Russian and Uzbek television are analogs of well-known Western television shows. For example, the 10th TV game "Поле чудес (pole chudes)" in Russia and "Mo'jizalar maydoni" in Uzbekistan is a licensed version of the popular American program "The Wheel of Fortune", which is successfully broadcast in many countries of the world; "Самое слабое звено (Samoye slaboye zveno)" is the Russian version of the famous English TV game "The Weakest Link", and the rating programs "Guess the Melody", "Navo" Uzbek variant, "Угадай мелодию (ugaday melodiyu)" Russian variant and "The Last Hero" are also based on American originals. Popular TV and radio formats that emerged on the Anglo-American soil are successfully adapting in last years in many countries: the number of programs using such basic media formats for the English-speaking mass media as talk-show, quiz game, phone-in program, candid camera, confession television, reality show, etc. growing steadily. Not only formats are borrowed, but also content. It is no secret that many Russian publications, which cover the latest in world cinema, popular music, as well as events in the world of show business, make their materials about the life of foreign stars, mainly "downloading" articles from the Internet sites of popular English-language magazines such as "Hello". Moreover, the previously practiced reference "based on the materials of the foreign press" is currently most often absent.

B. *Borrowings*

The impact of the Anglo-American mass media at the language level is manifested in a powerful wave of borrowing from English vocabulary. [8] From a conceptual point of view, borrowings, as a rule, reflect the most developed spheres of

activity within the framework of a particular national culture. So, on the pages of the British press, you can often find words in the French language that are used to denote objects of stylish life, high fashion and gastronomic delights, for example: *haute couture*, *soiree*, *clientele*, *vin de table*, etc. In turn, borrowings from English are conceptually related to areas such as business, politics, sports, computer technology, popular music, and youth culture. Here are some of the most striking examples: *management*, *show business*, *summit*, *promotion*, *halfback*, *file*, *drive*, *shoes*, *bottle* (youth slang).

Of course, some English-language borrowings have already become so firmly established in modern speech that replacing them with words of Russian origin seems rather difficult. This especially applies to those cases when an English word denotes a concept that is relatively new for Russian reality, the description of which by means of the Russian language requires certain lexical efforts. Thus, even with official support, the Russian name for the Anglo-American concept of "public relations" is unlikely to completely replace the English term "public relations" (PR) from everyday life. Moreover, a number of derivative words have been formed in the Russian language - PR, etc. In a significant number of media texts, the use of English borrowings is motivated by the desire to preserve a more economical language form, for example, the use of the English word "primaries" instead of the phrase "primary elections". The word of Scandinavian origin "ombudsman" is widely used in modern English to refer to people who represent the interests and defend the rights of citizens in various organizations, including the media. Moreover, in accordance with the requirements of political correctness, the "ombudsman" often turns into "ombudsperson". Analysis of linguistic processes at the interlinguistic level also allows us to make an assumption that there is a certain fashion for certain words and expressions spread through the media, and it is the media that contribute to the spread of a new, "fashionable" version of the use of the lexeme to other linguocultural areas (Tafari Vilma, 2009). Let's take, for example, the word "transparent", which is used in almost every speech of a modern Russian politician - a transparent budget, a transparent government, a transparent mechanism for the distribution of benefits, and so on. Traditionally combined with nouns denoting a physical entity - transparent air, transparent water, transparent glass, this adjective since the late 90s of the twentieth century has been actively used to denote such abstract concepts as budget, politics, financing, situation, political structures, organs authorities, etc. Moreover, this process was initiated precisely in the English-speaking region - first, "transparent policies", "transparent government", "transparent budget" appeared, and then, with the help of mass media, these options for compatibility migrated to other languages, including Russian. It is interesting to note that some politicians even demonstrate the use of the English version of the word by saying "транспарентный (transparetniy)" instead of "прозрачный (prozrachniy)". Thus, the Russian Minister of Defense, answering the questions of TV journalists, said

that the mechanism of conscription into the Russian army should be absolutely "transparent (транспарентным(transparentnim)". (Alekseeva,1994)

C. *Media texts*

The role of the media as channels of active linguistic interaction is also manifested in the use and dissemination of certain information and broadcasting styles. The concept of "information and broadcasting style" is directly related to mass communication and is used to denote that special tone of conversation with readers, listeners, viewers, which is characteristic of each particular mass media - newspaper, magazine, radio program or TV program. It is known that each media subject "speaks" with his audience in a certain tone, using stable media-stylistic and rhetorical means for addressing and text communication. So, for high-quality newspaper press one style of communication is characteristic, for popular - another, the style of British news broadcasting differs from the style of national TV news, etc. Like the musical mode, the tonality of a particular subject of the mass media can vary depending on a number of extralinguistic factors that can relate to political, historical, cultural, ideological, social spheres. Broadcast styles can be elevated formally, such as in national television news, utterly impersonal, such as the BBC's famous news broadcast style for objectivity, or deliberately familiar, such as most entertainment radio and television presenters. A comparative study of media texts shows that globalization, or rather the Anglo-Americanization of the modern media space, largely contributes to the partial borrowing and sometimes complete copying of certain information and broadcasting styles (Sherkovin, 2002). Thus, the changes in the period of restructure affected primarily the tone of communication between the post- media and their audience, which, in particular, resulted in a radical change in information and broadcasting styles. Much in the post- media discourse arose precisely due to the influence of the Anglo-American media speech. For example, the very common phrase today by TV news anchors "Оставайтесь с нами (ostovaytes s nami)" is nothing more than a translation of the famous English news cliché "Stay with us". Exploring the role of the media in the interaction of English and Russian media discourses, one cannot fail to mention the influence of the Russian language on English or Uzbek, which, of course, is not so noticeable, but still takes place in certain contexts. The most typical context is the so-called expat media, in other words, the press intended for Britons living and working abroad. Examples of such press are the newspapers "The Moscow Times" and "The Russian Journal", published in Moscow and intended both for foreigners living in Russia and for Russian citizens who speak English or "Visit Uzbekistan" which is intended for foreigners, "Tashkent Times", "Uzbekistan Today" can be an example to this category. Analysis of these publications shows that the texts of the mass media

immediately respond to the dominant linguocultural environment, integrating the most frequent and culturally significant vocabulary. Functioning in the Russian linguocultural area, English-language newspapers cover both international events and Russian reality, so it is natural that, talking about their "Russian experience", foreign correspondents try to "decorate" their material with original vocabulary conveying the specifics of national culture. Grandma, comrade, gentlemen, tusovka, girl - these and similar lexical units are introduced into the English text without translation to describe the realities of Russian or Uzbek life, to convey the national flavor. Thus, the use of Russian or Uzbek words, realia in English-language newspaper texts is always strictly motivated. Moreover, it should be noted that in some cases, despite the presence of the appropriate word necessary to designate a particular phenomenon of Russian reality, in English foreign journalists prefer to use the word of the Russian or Uzbek language, thus emphasizing intercultural differences, the discrepancy between the semantic boundaries of the concept in Foreign and English cultural traditions.

For example, the Russian word "бабушка (grandmother)" in the English spelling "babushka" is quite often found in the English-language texts of the mass media about Russia; linguistic and cultural connotations that cannot be conveyed using the English word of the corresponding meaning - grandmother, granny. Analysis of the role of the mass media at the intra-linguistic involves the study of the influence of the media on the functioning of the language within the framework of one linguistic-cultural area. Speaking about linguistic processes, which are triggered by the mass media, first of all, the following can be distinguished:

- 1) a tendency to blur clear stylistic boundaries
- 2) the spread of colloquial style norms in the basic corpus of media speech (news, information analytics, commentary)
- 3) replication of erroneous speech use (incorrect stress, grammatical errors, incorrect combination)
- 4) a decrease in the speech norm due to the use of jargon, profanity, etc.

The tendency to erase clear stylistic distinctions within the media speech corpus is noted by many researchers, both Russian and foreign. Perhaps this tendency is due to the extraordinary mobility and dynamism of the genre-typological paradigm of media discourse itself. The main types of media texts are news, information analytics (comment and analysis), journalism (features) and advertising, being in constant interaction and immediate temporal and spatial proximity (journalism and information and analytical programs are interrupted by advertising, news side by side with comments, etc.) naturally influence each other. Sometimes this leads to the emergence

of new genre-stylistic hybrids such as "infotainment" (Dobrosklonskaya, 2018) or "infomercial". The inclusion of entertainment or advertising components in news materials is dictated by the same key desire of mass communication - to attract the largest possible audience. Experts also note the convergence of the norms of oral and written speech in the media, which, apparently, is due to the functional and technological features of the discursive practices of mass communication themselves. So, the production and distribution of media texts includes such special techniques as reading from a crawl line, translating the primary oral text (for example, an interview) into a written publication form, integrating spontaneous speech and prepared speech, mixing conversational and literary styles. For example, the author of the well-known book "Live Russian Speech from the TV Screen" Lapteva (2003) writes:

"The influence of the sounding media on linguistic processes can hardly be overestimated. Now the language of the press and sounding media is becoming less and less close to the book-written type of literary language. Informational and official television speech experience a tremendous impact of the oral-speech element, there is an uncontrolled mixing of literary and oral-spoken speech features, which contributes to a general decline in speech culture."

Indeed, modern speech culture, the state and movement of the language norm are largely determined such basic properties of mass communication as multiple repetition and huge audience coverage. Unfortunately, we can say that the well-known proverb "what is written with a pen, cannot be cut down with an ax" is applicable today to the electronic media, in particular, to television. Speech sounding from the TV screen is perceived as the norm, and only a sensitive ear of a specialist is able to detect and pay attention to such linguistic "errors" (Lapteva, 2003, p.3).

IV. CONCLUSION

An active study of the properties of media speech began in the second half of the twentieth century, when the attention of scientists began to attract the most diverse aspects of the use of language in the media: from linguistic and pragmatic to functional and semiotic. The structure and content of media speech were studied within the framework of a variety of schools and areas: from the point of view of sociolinguistics, pragmatics, semiotics, psycholinguistics, functional stylistics, discourse analysis, content analysis, cognitive linguistics, as well as within the framework of such relatively new areas as "critical linguistics" and cultural linguistics.

The language of the media is the entire corpus of texts produced and distributed by the media; secondly, it is a stable intralingual system characterized by a certain set of linguistic-stylistic properties and features; and, finally, thirdly, it is a special sign system of a mixed type with a certain ratio of verbal and audiovisual components

specific to each of the media: print, radio, television, and the Internet. Let us illustrate these definitions with appropriate contexts. "Possessing high prestige and the most modern means of dissemination, the language of the media plays the role of a kind of model of the national language in the information society. It largely shapes literary norms, linguistic tastes and preferences, influences the perception of politics, ideology, art and literature". "Mass information is a global text that unites different linguistic communities with their social linguistic structures. Despite the difference in linguistic systems understood linguistically, mass information has a fundamental unity of meaning and direction of content". "Television speech is a very complexly organized set of varieties that are embodied in various genres. At the same time, the tendency to an increase and expansion of "free" genres is directly related to an increase in the effectiveness of the impact of television speech, with the most complete manifestation of the function of influence, which, along with the function of communication, is the leading one in the language of the mass media".

So, the key importance for the development of the general concept of the language of the media are the approaches when the language of the media is understood as

- a) as a stable intralingual system, characterized by a certain set of linguistic-stylistic properties and features,
- b) as a special sign system of a mixed type with a certain ratio of verbal and audiovisual components, specific for each of the media.

It was within the framework of these definitions that the content and internal structure of the modern concept of "language of the media" were formed. The theoretical basis of the concept of the language of the media is a systematic study of a stable range of issues related to the use of language in the field of mass communication, such as:

- what is the impact of mass communication on the ratio of oral and written forms of speech,
- how the mass nature of the message affects the movement of the language norm,
- what is the language of mass information from the point of view of functionalistic differentiation,
- what are the criteria for the typological classification of media texts,
- what is the specificity of the languages of specific media

- newspapers, magazine press, radio, television, the Internet, as well as the languages of so-called media-conditioned systems

- advertising and connections with the public.

And influence of the media on the course of language processes by researchers and in relation to other European languages - English, French, German, Spanish, Italian. Thus, we can conclude that the role played by the mass media in the dynamics of language development is enormous. Having become one of the main spheres of speech use, the mass media today largely determine the nature and properties of the modern state of the language. The reflection of these processes in academic science was expressed, in particular, in the formation and consolidation of the concept of "language of the media".

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